

MIGRATION FACT FROM PERSPECTIVE OF TURKISH PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS AND ITS EFFECT ON EDUCATION

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Abstract:

Migration can be regarded as a social phenomenon by changing the policies of social life and countries. Both the whole world and Turkey act as a scene for diverse and intense migration mobility in recent years. Escape way of economy, changes in political and social life, readjustment of borders in Eastern Europe and developments in Middle East have accelerated individual and massive migration movements. It is clear that the immigration phenomenon and its multicultural life and effects will continue to transform for many years. It is important to determine the migration perceptions of prospective teachers who will prepare generations for such an age of transformation. The aim of the study is to examine migration fact and effects of migration on education from prospective teachers' points of view. To answer the main statement of the research, two sub-questions were formed. 1) With which metaphors migration fact is explained by prospective teachers? Which categories can be formed in terms of common features of metaphors revealed by prospective teachers? 2) What are opinions of prospective teachers on effects of migration fact on educational system? In this research phenomenologic pattern method was used. The prospective teachers were asked a metaphor question in parallel with research questions and an open-ended question. The data was decoded by content analysis method. 152 prospective teachers participated into the study. As a *result*, categories of "new life", "psychological dimension", "socio-cultural dimension", "child and woman abuse", "tragedies experienced during migration", "migration geography" and "economic dimension" were formed from the metaphors produced relating to migration fact by the prospective teachers. The prospective teachers produced both positive and negative metaphors, however most of metaphors were negative. Categories of "education programs", "future of education",

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“social-emotional education for social agreement” and “school structures and management relationship” were formed based on opinions of the prospective teachers relating to the effects of migration fact on Turkish educational system.

Keywords: migration, education, metaphor, prospective teachers

1. Introduction

Migration fact is accepted as individual or massive movement of people from a place of settlement to another place of settlement for social, political, economic or cultural reasons (Şahin, 2001). This displacement can sometimes comprise a certain time, or sometimes a lifetime (Aksoy, 2012). The migration having a history as past as human history and understood to continue in the future is a fact, which concerns all regions of the world, having economic, cultural, social and educational outcomes (Doğan, 1988).

Migration Concept and Its Development: On general examination, migration movements take place voluntarily or compulsorily. Problems such as desires to have better condition in another place by leaving a place of settlement with economic, social or educational targets are highlighted in optional or voluntary migrations, while there are problems of geographical conditions, natural disasters, conflicts, wars and discriminations are highlighted in compulsory migrations (Parnwell, 1993, cited in Buz 2004). The migration is called as “internal migration” when taken place within a country and as “external migration” or “international migration” when taken place between countries (Aksoy, 2012).

On examination of history of migrations, migrations took place from Middle Asia to Anatolia due to climate changes, and sometimes from Ireland to North America in 19th century due to plant diseases. In the late 20th century and in 21st century, the most common reason of migration is economy and security (Erdoğan & Kaya, 2015). In order for better understanding of migration waves being one of determinatives of 21st century world, it is required to examine political, economic and social changes in 20th century.

20th century is handled in three periods as 1914-1945 “Disaster Age”; 1945-1970 “Gold Age”; 1980-1990s “Crisis age”. There were two world wars between 1914-1945 Disaster Age years, and this age witnessed massive losses and deep economic crises. The most important migration wave in this period was by Jewish and other oppressed groups’ leaving Europe as a result of Nazi implementations. The disaster age was followed by approximately 30 years of extraordinary development and social transformation. High welfare level acquired in the “Gold Age” was shared with justice concerns with public working particularly in rich countries, while injustice took over

once again towards the end of the century (Hobsbawm, 2017). During this period, a great amount of people migrated from III. World countries to industrialized countries for a better life (Kaya, 2003).

During transition from 1980s to 1990s, collapse of bipolar world caused a deep crisis. It was immediately understood that this crisis would deeply affect political and social life along with economic life, and it would disrupt the international system having stability for almost forty years (Hobsbawm, 2017). Particularly recession in developed countries after mid-1970s led to initiation for tight migration policies in developed countries. Legal migrants to developed countries in 1990s and 2000s were consisted mainly of highly qualified individuals (Kaya, 2003). In this respect, escape way of economy, changes in political and social life, readjustment of borders in Eastern Europe and developments in Middle East have accelerated individual and massive migration movements.

Turkey and Migration: It is an acknowledged fact that Turkey is one of the countries being affected by migration due to its geopolitical location. In establishment years of Turkish Republic, population was significantly renewed due to international population exchange. At the same years, high amounts of cognate migration were encountered particularly from Europe, and this mobility was accompanied by internal migrations from the country to town and workforce migrations (Erdoğan & Kaya, 2015).

A number of developments such as Cold War caused by the bipolar world, then globalization and membership process of Turkey into European Union have affected national and international environment, and changed migrant and refugee profile coming to Turkey significantly. This situation has led Turkey to become a country receiving and giving migration, and also a “migration passage country” to use while migration towards different countries (İçduygu, Erder & Gençkaya, 2014).

The last event added into migration history of Turkey is permission to Syrians to come into Turkey as a result of expansion of humanitarian crisis experienced from 2011 to our day in Syria. According to the data of Migration Administration General Directorate (MAGD, 2016a), number of Syrian citizens who were put under temporary protection has reached to 3.049.879. With this number, Turkey ranks as the first in migrant admission. Compared to Europe and America accepting refugees, it is seen that Turkey has embraced tremendous amount of migrants (Syrian Refugees, 2016).

Migration Studies: Both the whole world and Turkey act as a scene for diverse and intense migration mobility in recent years. It is understood that this mobility has pretty important socio-cultural, economic and educational outcomes. In globalized world, it is obvious that these outcomes will affect not only the migrated country, but

also all world countries. It is highly important that these effects are determined in advance and necessary precautions are taken. Studies relating to migration fact having a fairly old past started to have interest in Western Europe and USA only after Second World War. It is a field of study for almost the last 20 years in Turkey. During this process, centers and institutes relating to migration have been established, scientific studies and conferences have been conducted relating to the subject (Erdoğan & Kaya, 2015).

On examination of Turkey literature, studies on both internal and external migration are seen. In studies examining internal migration, focuses were on unemployment, irregular structuring, adaptation problems, academic successes, school attendance problems, behavior problems of children of immigrating families, crowded classroom structures, disadvantages caused by poverty for utilizing educational services and expectations of immigrating parents on education (Han, 2010; İçli, 1999; Karakuş, 2006; Tezcan, 1994; Uluocak, 2009). In studies examining international migration, it is understood that subjects are investigated such as refugeeism, social effects of refugee behavior, living conditions of Syrians in Turkey, international migration policies, effects of migration of psychology of an individual, brain drain etc. (Aksoy, 2012; Buz, 2004; Gökçan, Açıkyıldız & Ataman, 2015; İçduygu, Erder & Gençkaya, 2014; Kaya, 2003; Şahin, 2001)

Migration and Education: Migration and education are intermixed decision in many aspects. Education and skill acquisition of an individual have an important role in many stages of migration process. Welfare level of an individual in the migrated country is determined by educational background and acquired information and skills (Dustmann & Glitz, 2011). While it is easier for an individual to have required educational opportunities in voluntary migrations taken place for a better life motivation, it gets harder to reach educational opportunities in compulsory migrations. According to the data of the UN Refugee Agency (UNHCR, 2016), 65.6 million people all around the world had to leave their place of settlement. More than half of them consisted of children under age of 18. UNHCR defends inclusion of refugee children into national educational system as a sustainable approach for enabling permanent education. Turkey hosts almost 3 million Syrians. Almost 1 million school age Syrian children are living under temporary protection. Number of Syrian students having education in public schools is 169 thousand 10 and number of Syrian students having education in temporary education centers is 294 thousand 112. It is reported that totally 459.521 people utilize educational services (MAGD, 2016b).

An important portion of refugee children experience problems such as financial impossibility, language, inability to have friends, etc. in schools. Moreover, there is a

serious ratio of child labor among these children. This situation may prevent refugee children from having a healthy education and adaptation to this new culture. Considering that a great amount of refugees in Turkey are children, education of children becomes a highly serious subject (Sayın, Usanmaz, & Aslangiri, 2016).

Migration fact and Metaphor: Migration fact and resulting multicultural life and effect are obvious to last for many years with change. It was seen necessary to reveal opinions of prospective teachers who prepare generations to such a transformation age relating to migration concept. Metaphors have an important place in revelation of perceptions and views, i.e., cognitive and affective features (Gültekin 2013) of prospective teachers relating to migration. Metaphor is a feature of language and a tool of poetical imagination or elocution for many people. However, metaphor, on the contrary, has a common and important place in expression of actions and thoughts along with language in daily life, and leads them (Lakoff & Johnson, 2015). Greek correspondence of metaphor “metapherein” means “transmitting”, “carrying”. Metaphors take words from their ordinary contexts and displace it to another context. Moreover, metaphors are reflections of a period, a culture and an environment, and provide information relating to activities and thoughts of its users (Draaisma, 2014). In this respect, it is expected that revealing meanings ascribed to migration concept by means of metaphors by prospective teachers will contribute to Turkish Education System and the literature.

1.1 Purpose of the Study

Purpose of the study is to examine migration fact and effects of migration on education from points of view of prospective teachers. In line with this purpose, two research questions were formed:

- 1) With which metaphors migration fact is explained by prospective teachers? Which categories can be formed in terms of common features of metaphors revealed by prospective teachers?
- 2) What are opinions of prospective teachers on effects of migration fact on educational system?

2. Method

The study was formed in phenomenologic pattern method and content analysis was used (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2014). The participants were asked a metaphor question in parallel with sub-study questions and an open-ended question, and the acquired data was decoded with content analysis.

2.1 Study Group

The study group consisted of prospective teachers having education in Faculty of Education of Celal Bayar University in 2015-2016 educational year and having education in pedagogical formation program opened within the body of this university. 176 prospective teachers participated into the study. On examination of the forms, 24 forms were cancelled for reasons such as incomplete filling and blank-leaving. Analyses were conducted over 152 forms. Totally 152 prospective teachers participated into the study as 29 from Psychological Counseling and Guidance program, 27 from Science Teaching program, 25 from Social Sciences Teaching program, 23 from Mathematics program, 24 from Turkish Language and Literature program and 24 from English Language and Literature program. 80 of participants were female, and 72 were male prospective teachers.

2.2 Data Collection Tools

The metaphor question and open-ended question prepared in accordance with the purpose of the study and sub-study questions were asked to the students in written form. These questions were as follows:

1. Migration is like/similar to because
2. What do you think about effects of migration fact on Turkish educational system?

2.3 Data Collection and Analysis

The metaphor question and open-ended question relating to migration concept was asked to the prospective teachers participating into the study by means of a form, and they were provided with sufficient time to explain their opinions in written form. Metaphors of the prospective teachers relating to migration concepts and answers relating to the effect of migration fact on Turkish educational system were analyzed with content analysis method. The main purpose in the content analysis is to gather similar data within frame of certain concepts and themes and to interpret them by arranging them to be understandable by the reader (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2008). Also, metaphor analysis stages of Saban (2008) were used in analysis of the metaphors. The metaphors of the participants were analyzed under third stages:

Denotation (coding) and Elimination Stage: In this stage, metaphors used in explaining migration fact of the prospective teachers were examined. It is handled whether metaphor can be clearly associated with migration concept or not, and statements indication metaphor feature were listed. The forms incapable of providing

valid metaphor or left blank were eliminated (N:37). 100 of the metaphors were deemed acceptable; and it was understood that some metaphors were used by more than one prospective teachers.

Compilation and category development stage: Perceptions of the prospective teachers relating to migration fact were examined with 100 produced metaphors and explanations. The metaphors were analyzed in terms of the “relationship with metaphor subject and source”. The metaphors associated with similar themes in terms of explanations and qualifications were classified under totally seven categories.

Reliability and validity provision stage: Validity and reliability are the most important criteria to be attained in qualitative studies (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2008). With this purpose, the study process included detailed information relating to data collection and analysis. All produced metaphors were listed. The metaphors, explanations relating to the metaphors and categories formed based on these were presented to expert opinions of two academicians working in said field. Subjects with agreement and disagreement were discussed, and necessary corrections were made.

Information relating to data collection and analysis were explained in detail in the study process. Moreover, direct quotations from the prospective teachers were made relating to metaphors in categories formed based on the metaphors produced in the study. An expert academician in the field was included into the study for confirmation of categories, themes, produced metaphors and explanations relating to these metaphors and accuracy of the categories. The academicians made a matching with these metaphors and categories. After the expert opinions taken within scope of the study, discussions were made for non-overlapping metaphors. Afterwards, the themes and metaphors forming these were finalized. On calculation of reliability coefficient of this qualitative study, reliability formula of Miles and Huberman (1994) ($\text{Reliability} = \text{Consensus} / (\text{Consensus} + \text{Dissensus})$) was utilized. Reliability coefficient for these categories was detected as 87%.

3. Findings

The acquired data were presented in two main sections based on the study questions. The first section included metaphors produced by the participant prospective teachers relating to migration fact and categories formed based on these, and the second section included findings acquired from answers of the prospective teachers relating to questions asked relating to the effects of migration fact on education.

3.1 Results relating to migration metaphors:

The metaphors produced relating to migration fact by the prospective teachers were presented as a general table in the first stage. Afterwards, categories were formed based on common features of the acquired metaphors, quotations of the prospective teachers were made for better explanation of the categories. The metaphors produced relating to migration fact were presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Metaphors used in explaining “migration” concept by the prospective teachers

<i>Metaphors</i>				
Aegean sea	co-wife concept	ghetto	mosaic	stolen life
ant	death	ghost	newborn baby (f:5)	stork
autumn (f:4)	disaster(f:4)	girl with red mantle	nightmare	storm(f:2)
baby Aylan (f:4)	divorce	Greek islands	paper tissue	suitcase
beggar	dry stream bed	green card	parasite	Syria (f:6)
bird (f:13)	earthquake (f:5)	guardian angel	peacock	Şanlı Urfa
birth	England	Hatay	rain water	tent
bottomless well	epidemic	hell(f:2)	rainbow (colorful)	The Usa
brain drain	Europe	homelessness	river water	to be reborn (f:9)
broken family	evolution	horror tunnel	rope-broken elevator	to change shell
broomed witch	falling leaf	Iraq	sandglass	train terminal
burst boat	flood (f:5)	İstanbul (f:2)	sea	travel
bus terminal	flow of water	key	shanty house	tree disassembled from roots
chameleon	flying balloon	Kilis	shelter	vampire
child bride	forceful marriage	landslide	sky	virus(f:2)
child worker	France	lesbos island	slavery	war (3)
cloud	freedom	life vests	snowslide	water in desert
cockboat	garbage	lottery	southeast	wave
collapsed wall	Gazi Antep	Middle east	speechlessness	wind
cornflower	Germany	missing toy	spider web	wreck

As seen in Table 1, 100 metaphors were produced relating to migration concepts. Some of these metaphors (Baby Aylan f=4, earthquake f=4, flood f=4, etc.) was expressed by more than one participants. At the end of the analysis of the detected metaphors, the categories in the Figure 1 were reached. The metaphors and their explanations associated with categories were given below.

Figure 1: Categories Formed relating to Migration Concept

New Life Category: In the new life category, metaphors of key, suitcase, evolution, guardian angel, sky, rainbow (colorful), ghost, bird, river water, traveler, freedom, shelter, peacock, newborn baby, to be reborn, to change shell, water in desert, mosaic, lottery, travel and stork were produced. Totally 21 metaphors were included into this category. With these metaphors, aspect of providing a more positive life of migration fact was highlighted by the prospective teachers. For example, in bird metaphor as the most repeated metaphor, a prospective teacher stated: “migration is like bird, because birds move for better life conditions in accordance with seasonal conditions, just like desire to seek better in migration fact”. Some prospective teachers highlighted colorful and multicultural life provided to people by migration fact in their metaphors. A prospective teacher stated: “migration is like mosaic, because migrations contain cultural diversity, different lives, i.e., mosaic”, while another one stated: “migration represents array of bright colors in peacock and new lives”.

Psychological Dimension Category: In this category, 23 metaphors were reached as homelessness, divorce, bottomless well, flood, earthquake, broomed witch, autumn, falling leaf, birth, sea, death, war, rain water, missing toy, tree disassembled from roots, hell, flying balloon, stolen life, dry stream bed, disaster, sandglass and horror tunnel. In metaphors collected under this category, prospective teachers mainly focused on the effect of migration life on psychological world of individuals. A prospective teacher stated: “Migration is like a tree disassembled from its roots; a tree lives long in a place of settlement, and lives less when removed from its roots, and an individual forced to migrate becomes unhappy wherever he/she goes”, while another one stated “migration is like earthquake, because it destroys an individual’s dreams and hopes”.

Socio-Cultural Dimension Category: Totally 19 metaphors were included into this category as speechlessness, culture shock, shanty house, landslide, cloud, epidemic, chameleon, broken family, disaster, snow slide, virus, wreck, flood, flow of water, parasite, wind, ghetto, waves and spider web. In this category, the prospective teachers emphasized social and cultural changes seen in societies affected from migrations with their metaphors. For example, a prospective teacher likened migration to virus and continued as follows: *“migration is like a virus, a virus destroys a body just like migration destroys and consumes a society”*. Another one stated: *“migration is like snow slide, if not controlled, migration movements turn into an unstoppable snow slide”*. Relating to the situation to arise in case of directionlessness of migration, a prospective teacher stated: *“Migration is like flow/mobility of water, water provides life to places where it goes with an order, and it harms when it moves as a flood”*. According to one another, *“migration is like an epidemic, an epidemic arising in a region may affect people rapidly and expand among regions”*. A prospective teacher likening migration to a parasite stated: *“... there are beneficial and harmful parasites. It may provide benefit and harm to migrated country”*.

Child and Woman Abuse Category: Seven metaphors were produced in this category as child worker, child bride, forceful marriage, co-wife concept, girl with red mantle, paper tissue and beggar. It was understood that the prospective teachers using these metaphors highlighted effects of migration on children and women. A prospective teacher stated *“migration is like a girl with red mantle, it carries innocence and despair of children forced to migrate...”* while another stated *“migration is like a paper tissue, it goes from hand to hand, it carries sorrow of a child, like sorrows in migration”* while another stated *“migration is like a child worker, working child loses his/her childhood and hopes of future, just like losses in migrations”*, and lastly a prospective teacher explained abuses of women during migration as *“migration is like being a co-wife, a number of women who had to leave their homes due to war in our country and other countries become co-wives for another woman with economic and social impositions. Being co-wife during migration is an unpleasant outcome of survival struggle”*.

Category of Tragedies Experienced during Migration: The category of tragedies experienced during migration consisted of metaphors of baby Aylan, Aegean Sea, life vests, tent, bus terminal, burst boat, cockboat, train terminal and collapsed wall. Totally 10 metaphors were included in this category. In this category expressing tragic events experienced during migration, a prospective teacher likened migration to the baby Aylan losing his life as a consequence of capsizing of boats while passing to Greek islands in Aegean Sea, and explained his/her view as *“migration represents misfortunes and negativities experiences by children”*. Another prospective teacher stated *“migration is like a burst boat, it send people thereon to depth of water, just like tragic ends of people*

migrating for a better life", while another one stated *"Migration is like a life vest, it is a change to survive, but it may not always work. If you encounter an opportunistic and evil people, a life vest may end your life"*, thereby highlighting the disaster experienced on passage from Aegean and Mediterranean Sea to Europe.

Migration Geography Category: 17 metaphors were included into this category as USA, Germany, Europe, France, England, İstanbul, Middle East, Southeast, Syria, Iraq, Greece, Greek Island, Lesbos Island, Şanlıurfa, Kilis, Gaziantep and Hatay. In the migration geography category, provinces of Turkey neighboring Middle East and Syria were metaphorized with respect to traces of migration on socio-psychological structure, and America and Europe were metaphorized as new life dreams. For example, a prospective teacher stated *"Migration is like Middle East, both have inherent tears and tragedy"*, while another one stated *"migration is like Syria, it is dominated by conflict and chaos"*. On the other hand, it was understood that the prospective teachers perceived western countries as new life opportunities. For example, a prospective teacher stated *"migration is like America, it is a dream for a better life"*, while another one stated *"migration is like Europe, both are doors opening to a new life"*.

Economic Dimension Category: Seven metaphors were produced in this category as slavery, nightmare, green card, ant, garbage, vampire and rope-broken elevator. Metaphors and explanations revealing the relationship between migration and economy by the prospective teachers were included into this category. It was understood that the prospective teachers reflected economic disadvantages caused by migration. A prospective teacher stated *"migration is like a vampire, it sucks efforts of people like a vampire"*, while another one likened migration to slavery and continued as follows: *"Migration is like slavery, because it takes place involuntarily, just like a slave having to do something he/she does not want, working for peanuts"*. On the other hand, some prospective teachers perceived migration as an economic opportunity. For example, a prospective teacher stated *"migration is like a green card, it creates opportunity for a better income"*.

3.2 Results relating to Effect of Migration Fact on Educational System:

The prospective teachers were asked the question "What do you think about the effects of migration fact on educational system?" Answers from the prospective teachers were classified under four categories. The acquired categories were shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Categories Formed relating to Effects of Migration Fact on Educational System

According to responses, it was understood that the prospective teachers regarded language educations for migrants as a priority in *Curriculum category*. It was highlighted that educational plans relating to Turkish education and their own language were required. Another point in this category was increase of course hours of rearrangement of psychology, creative drama, citizenship, sociology and philosophy courses and readjustment of their contents in order that migrant children adapted to new environment and Turkish friends. It was expressed that school-based curriculum development studies were required in regions receiving intense migration.

On examination of codes of *Future of Education* category, it was expressed that this cultural diversity reached in Turkish education system after migrations would create opportunity for a more global education, multicultural education structures would be required, and there would be difficulties in management of differences such as language, race, etc. to arise in heterogeneous class structures. Moreover, it was seen as a requirement that precautions were taken for qualified population lost due to brain drains.

According to codes of Social-Emotional Education for Social Agreement Category, it was stated by the prospective teachers that peace and dispute resolution, world citizenship, and respect for all differences education in schools, and psychosocial educations for individuals coming from a war environment and losing their relatives were necessary. On examination of codes of *school structures and school management relationships* category, schooling, school attendance problems of migrant children, discipline problems in schools in intense migration-receiving regions was expressed by the prospective teachers frequently. Lastly, it was highlighted that there might be communication problems due to language and cultural differences with migrant parents.

4. Conclusion

The study firstly reveals metaphors of migration fact by the prospective teachers. Secondly, the opinions of the prospective teachers relating to the effects of migration fact on education system were detected. It was determined in the first stage of the study that the prospective teachers produced totally 100 metaphors in explaining migration fact. According to Draaisma (2014), metaphors are products of the culture and environment of living and they can provide information about ideas and activities of their producers. From this point of view, migration metaphors may be accepted as a strong predictor of opinion, thought and actions of the prospective teachers relating to the subject.

In this study, baby Aylan, earthquake, İstanbul, bird, war, flood, snow slide, parasite, virus, nightmare, child worker, child bride, burst boat, slavery, vampire, Syria, newborn baby, to be reborn, bird, mosaic and rainbow were some of the metaphors. On examination of these produced metaphors, it was seen that the prospective teachers produced both positive and negative metaphors, however mostly metaphors were negative. These metaphors shows similarity with harmonization, transplantation and viral propagation metaphors stated to be commonly used in explaining migration by Macdonald (2013).

Secondly, the prospective teachers understood migration mostly as migration from Middle East, particularly Syria. It is obvious that reason of this perception is the migration wave leading towards neighboring countries, particularly Turkey from civil war and humanitarian crisis in Syria in 2011. The effect of this migration wave on Turkish society has been revealed in a number of studies, just like this study (Gökçan, Açıkyıldız, & Ataman, 2015; Kaypak & Bimay, 2016; Sayın, Usanmaz & Aslangiri, 2016). Thirdly, there are rare metaphors produced by the prospective teachers relating to internal migration and brain drain. According to the statistics of Turkish Statistical Institute (TSI, 2016), 25% of 1950 Turkish population lived in countries, while 92.1% of the population lived in countries in 2015. A serious migration from towns to countries in the last 30-35 years in particular, due to accessibility to better education opportunities, economic, social and political reasons. It is obvious that this migration has significant effects on Turkey's social, economic life and education system (Dücan, 2016). On the other hand, Turkey ranks as the 24th country among 34 countries with the most frequent brain drain migration (Kaya, 2003). Scientific, economic and social consequences of brain drain cannot be ignored.

Considering the metaphors produced by the prospective teachers relating to migration fact, "new life", "psychological dimension", "socio-cultural dimension",

“child and woman abuse”, “tragedies experienced during migration”, “migration geography” “economic dimension” categories were formed. In the “new life” category, aspect of providing a more positive life of migration fact for people was highlighted. It is understood that the prospective teachers understand migration fact as a voluntary displacement for better life standard and job opportunities (Kaya, 2003).

In the “psychological dimension” category, mainly the effects of migration life on psychological life of migrants were focused. Generally, the prospective teachers thought that migration would have negative effects on psychological health of the prospective teachers. On examination of the literature, particularly external, compulsory migrations were stated to be a fact that had effects on human psychology (Aker, et al.2002; Şahin, 2001). It was indicated that compulsory migration would cause development of mental illnesses, compulsory migration would case a traumatic life and cause depression and other anxiety disorders (Aker, et al., 2002).

The “socio-cultural dimension” category is oriented towards changes caused by migration on social and cultural lives of societies. It was understood that mostly negative metaphors such as disaster, snowslide, virus, wreck, flood were produced. Migration metaphors examined by Cunningham-Parmeter (2011) and some metaphors under this category showed similarity. The author argued that flood and invasion metaphors were used in explaining migration and migration in society was defined in terms of danger, attack and crime. Also the author defended that it was an alienating language.

In the “child and woman abuse” category, troubles experienced by children and women during migration and injustices experienced by women in terms of social gender roles were highlighted. The prospective teachers perceived children and women as the most disadvantaged groups of migration. These results show similarity with results of many studies on the field (Şeker & Uçan, 2016; Sayın, Usanmaz, & Aslangiri, 2016). It is of a critical importance that woman- and child-focused studies are highlighted in migration studies.

In the “tragedies experienced during migration” category, particularly disasters experienced during travel to hope were highlighted. Unfortunately, baby Aylan and disasters in Aegean Sea were the most important metaphors of this category. In the “migration geography” category, America and Europe were regarded as a door for a better life, while provinces of Turkey neighboring Middle East and Syria were perceived as representatives of negative effects of chaos on individual and society.

In the “economic dimension” category, the prospective teachers marked the relationship between migration and economy. The metaphors mostly emphasized battening of labor and experienced economic troubles, while some prospective teachers

paid attention to economic opportunities with green card metaphor. Cunningham-Parmeter (2011) revealed economic contribution of migration, rather than negative metaphors such as flood, invasion, alienation. Special circumstances of migrated country and socio-economic structure of migrants are determinatives of migration and economy relationships (Kaya, 2003).

The opinions relating to the effects of migration fact on Turkish education system were examined under categories of “education programs”, “future of education”, “social-emotional education for social agreement” and “school structures and management relationship”. It was emphasized that conversion of education programs, peace and conflict resolution education, language teaching approaches, increasing course hours of psychology, language, citizenship, sociology, philosophy courses and providing opportunity for global education of migration would have effects on schooling and school attendance problems of migrants, heterogeneous class structures and their managements. These acquired results are also supported by the literature ((Dustmann & Glitz, 2011; Dücan, 2016; Han, 2010; İçli, 1999; Karakuş, 2006; Tezcan, 1994; Uluocak, 2009 Sayın, Usanmaz, & Aslangiri, 2016).

It is obvious that all components of education system should be revised based on migration fact. Also, it is of a critical importance that teacher and prospective teachers are supported under cultural conflict between “host’ cultures and migrant cultures, language differences and communication troubles experiences by migrant children; migrants and economic differences; academic differences with migrant students (Luchtenberg, 2004, cited in EUNEC, 2013) etc. subject titles.

Within the context of results acquired from this study, the following suggestions may be proposed:

- Similar and different aspects of migration fact and educational effects may be revealed by interviewing of psychological consultants working in schools affected by migration with teachers, managers, students and parents.
- Migration and education courses may be provided in faculties of education.
- Course contents about education in multicultural environments may be incorporated in faculties of education.
- Conflict resolution, common life, respect for differences subjects may be integrated into education programs.

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